

Survey on National Contributions to EOSC and Open Science 2024

This survey consists of questions for monitoring policies and practices for EOSC and Open Science at national (and/or regional, where applicable) level in Europe. The survey is divided into four sections: Policies; Practices; General; Feedback. The sections on policies and practices are further divided into eight categories that are relevant for EOSC and Open Science: Publications; Data; Software; Services; Infrastructure; Skills/ Training; Assessment; Engagement. The data collected through the survey will be published in the EOSC Observatory and EOSC Observatory Zenodo Community.

Policies

Publications

1. Does your country have a national policy on open access to publications?

- Yes
- No

1.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

1.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

1.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

1.3. Is there a specific policy on immediate open access to publications?

- Yes
- No

1.3.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

1.3.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

1.3.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

1.4. Is there a specific policy on retention of IPR on publications?

- Yes
- No

1.4.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

1.4.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

1.4.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

1.5. Is there a specific policy on open licensing of publications?

- Yes
- No

1.5.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

1.5.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

1.5.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

1.6. Please clarify your response if relevant

2. Does your country have a financial strategy on open access to publications?

- Yes
- No

2.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

3. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on open access to publications?

3.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

4. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on open access to publications?

4.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Data

5. Does your country have a national policy on data management?

- Yes
- No

5.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

5.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

5.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

5.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

6. Does your country have a financial strategy on data management?

- Yes
- No

6.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

7. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on data management?

7.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

8. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on data management?

8.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

9. Does your country have a national policy on FAIR data?

- Yes
- No

9.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

9.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

9.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

9.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

10. Does your country have a financial strategy on FAIR data?

- Yes
- No

10.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

11. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on FAIR data?

11.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

12. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on FAIR data?

12.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

13. Does your country have a national policy on open data?

- Yes

No

13.1. Is this policy mandatory?

Yes

No

13.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

13.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

13.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

14. Does your country have a financial strategy on open data?

Yes

No

14.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

15. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on open data?

15.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

16. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on open data?

16.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Software

17. Does your country have a national policy on Open-Source software?

Yes

No

17.1. Is this policy mandatory?

Yes

No

17.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

17.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

17.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

18. Does your country have a financial strategy on open-source software?

Yes

No

18.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

19. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on Open-Source software?

19.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

20. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on Open-Source software?

20.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Services

21. Does your country have a national policy on offering services through EOSC?

Yes

No

21.1. Is this policy mandatory?

Yes

No

21.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

21.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

21.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

22. Does your country have a financial strategy on offering services through EOSC?

Yes

No

22.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

23. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on offering services through EOSC?

23.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

24. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on offering services through EOSC?

24.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Infrastructure

25. Does your country have a national policy on connecting repositories to EOSC?

Yes

No

25.1. Is this policy mandatory?

Yes

No

25.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

25.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

25.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

26. Does your country have a financial strategy on connecting repositories to EOSC?

- Yes
- No

26.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

27. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on connecting repositories to EOSC?

27.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

28. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on connecting repositories to EOSC?

28.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

29. Does your country have a national policy on data stewardship?

- Yes
- No

29.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

29.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

29.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

29.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

30. Does your country have a financial strategy on data stewardship?

- Yes
- No

30.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

31. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on data stewardship?

31.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

32. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on data stewardship?

32.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

33. Does your country have a national policy on long-term data preservation?

- Yes
- No

33.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

33.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

33.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

33.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

34. Does your country have a financial strategy on long-term data preservation?

- Yes
- No

34.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

35. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on long-term data preservation?

35.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

36. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on long-term data preservation?

36.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Skills/Training

37. Does your country have a national policy on skills/training for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

37.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

37.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

37.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

37.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

38. Does your country have a financial strategy on skills/training for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

38.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

39. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on skills/training for Open Science?

39.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

40. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on skills/training for Open Science?

40.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Assessment

41. Does your country have a national policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

41.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

41.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

41.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

41.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

42. Does your country have a financial strategy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

42.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

43. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

43.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

44. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

44.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Engagement

45. Does your country have a national policy on citizen science?

- Yes
- No

45.1. Is this policy mandatory?

- Yes
- No

45.2. Is information on this policy available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

45.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

45.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

46. Does your country have a financial strategy on citizen science?

- Yes
- No

46.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

47. How many research-performing organisations in your country have a policy on citizen science?

47.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

48. How many research-funding organisations in your country have a policy on citizen science?

48.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Practices

Publications

49. Does your country have a national monitoring on open access to publications?

- Yes
- No

49.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

50. Does your country have use cases on open access to publications?

- Yes
- No

50.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

50.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

50.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

50.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

51. How much did your country financially invest in open access to publications in 2023 in millions of Euros?

51.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

52. How many publications were published in open access in your country in 2023?

Data

53. Does your country have a national monitoring on data management?

- Yes
- No

53.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

54. Does your country have use cases on data management?

- Yes
- No

54.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

54.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

54.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

54.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

55. How much did your country financially invest in data management in 2023 in millions of Euros?

55.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

56. How many and what percentage of national funding programmes which mandate the use of DMPs (in projects) were there in your country in 2023?

56.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

57. Does your country have a national monitoring on FAIR data?

Yes

No

57.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

58. Does your country have use cases on FAIR data?

Yes

No

58.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

58.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

58.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

58.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

59. How much did your country financially invest in FAIR data in 2023 in millions of Euros?

59.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

60. How many FAIR data sets were published in your country in 2023?

[This question is on pause for the future]

61. Does your country have a national monitoring on open data?

- Yes
- No

61.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

62. Does your country have use cases on open data?

- Yes
- No

62.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

62.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

62.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

62.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

63. How much did your country financially invest in open data in 2023 in millions of Euros?

63.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

64. How many open data sets were published in your country in 2023?

Software

65. Does your country have a national monitoring on Open-Source software?

- Yes
- No

65.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

66. Does your country have use cases on Open-Source software?

- Yes
- No

66.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

66.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

66.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

66.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

67. How much did your country financially invest in Open-Source software in 2023 in millions of Euros?

67.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

68. How many Open-Source software sets were published in your country in 2023?

[Data will be extracted from external source]

Services

69. Does your country have a national monitoring on offering services through EOSC?

- Yes
- No

69.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

70. Does your country have use cases on offering services through EOSC?

- Yes
- No

70.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

70.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

70.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

70.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

71. How much did your country financially invest in offering services through EOSC in 2023 in millions of Euros?

71.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

72. How many services were offered through EOSC in your country in 2023?

[Data will be extracted from external source]

Infrastructure

73. Does your country have a national monitoring on connecting repositories to EOSC?

- Yes
- No

73.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

74. Does your country have use cases on connecting repositories to EOSC?

- Yes
- No

74.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

74.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

74.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

74.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

75. How much did your country financially invest in connecting repositories to EOSC in 2023 in millions of Euros?

75.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

76. How many repositories were connected to EOSC in your country in 2023?

[Data will be extracted from external source]

77. Does your country have a national monitoring on data stewardship?

- Yes
- No

77.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

78. Does your country have use cases on data stewardship?

- Yes
- No

78.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

78.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

78.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

78.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

79. How much did your country financially invest in data stewardship in 2023 in millions of Euros?

79.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

80. How many and what percentage of national funding programmes which support data stewardship (in projects) were there in your country in 2023?

80.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

81. Does your country have a national monitoring on long-term data preservation?

- Yes
- No

81.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

82. Does your country have use cases on long-term data preservation?

- Yes
- No

82.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

82.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

82.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

82.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

83. How much did your country financially invest in long-term data preservation in 2023 in millions of Euros?

83.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

84. How many repositories offered long-term data preservation in your country in 2023?

Skills/Training

85. Does your country have a national monitoring on skills/training for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

85.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

86. Does your country have use cases on skills/training for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

86.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

86.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

86.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

86.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

87. How much did your country financially invest in skills/training for Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?

87.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

88. How many and what percentage of national funding programmes which support skills/training for Open Science (in projects) were there in your country in 2023?

88.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Assessment

89. Does your country have a national monitoring on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

89.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

90. Does your country have use cases on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

- Yes
- No

90.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

90.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

90.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

90.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

91. How much did your country financially invest in incentives/rewards for Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?

91.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

92. How many signatories of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment were there in your country in 2023?

[Data will be extracted from external source]

Engagement

93. Does your country have a national monitoring on citizen science?

- Yes
- No

93.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

94. Does your country have use cases on citizen science?

- Yes
- No

94.1. Please provide a short description of the use case

94.2. Is information on this use case available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

94.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

94.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

95. How much did your country financially invest in citizen science in 2023 in millions of Euros?

95.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

96. How many and what percentage of national funding programmes which support citizen science (in projects) were there in your country in 2023?

96.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Impact

Publications

97. Does your country have impact stories on open access to publications?

- Yes
- No

97.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

97.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

97.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

97.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

98. How many citations of open access publications were there in your country in 2023?

[Data will be extracted from external source]

Data

101. Does your country have impact stories on data management?

Yes

No

101.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

101.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

101.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

101.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

105. Does your country have impact stories on FAIR data?

Yes

No

105.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

105.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

105.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

105.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

106. How many citations of FAIR data sets were there in your country in 2023?

109. Does your country have impact stories on open data?

Yes

No

109.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

109.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

109.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

109.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

110. How many citations of open data sets were there in your country in 2023?

Software

113. Does your country have impact stories on Open-Source software?

- Yes
- No

113.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

113.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

113.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

113.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

114. How many citations of Open-Source software sets were there in your country in 2023?

Services

117. Does your country have impact stories on offering services through EOSC?

- Yes
- No

117.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

117.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

117.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

117.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

118. How many services offered through EOSC were used in your country in 2023?

Infrastructure

121. Does your country have impact stories on connecting repositories to EOSC?

- Yes
- No

121.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

121.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

121.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

121.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

125. Does your country have impact stories on data stewardship?

- Yes
- No

125.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

125.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

125.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

125.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

129. Does your country have impact stories on long-term data preservation?

- Yes
- No

129.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

129.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

129.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

129.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

Skills/Training

133. Does your country have impact stories on skills/training for Open Science?

- Yes

No

133.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

133.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

133.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

133.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

Assessment

137. Does your country have impact stories on incentives/rewards for Open Science?

Yes

No

137.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

137.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

Yes

No

137.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

137.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

138. How many action plans for the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment were there in your country in 2023?

Engagement

141. Does your country have impact stories on citizen science?

- Yes
- No

141.1. Please provide a short description of the impact story.

141.2. Is information on this impact story available publicly on the web?

- Yes
- No

141.2.1. Please provide links to the relevant webpages

141.3. Please clarify your response if relevant

General

145. How many research-performing organisations are there in your country?

145.1. For how many of these research-performing organisations there is information provided in this survey?

145.2. Please clarify your response if relevant

146. How many research-funding organisations are there in your country?

146.1. For how many of these research-funding organisations there is information provided in this survey?

146.2. Please clarify your response if relevant

147. How much did your country financially invest in total in EOSC and Open Science in 2023 in millions of Euros?

147.1. Please clarify your response if relevant

Feedback

148. Do you have any suggestions on how to improve this survey for future iterations?